

Review

The Efficacy and Safety of Auricular Acupuncture for Preoperative Anxiety: A Review of Randomised Controlled Trials.

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Abstract

Background: Preoperative anxiety is a common issue for patients undergoing surgical procedures, leading to increased stress, heightened pain perception, and a greater need for anaesthesia. While pharmacological interventions have been the primary method of management, their side effects have led to growing interest in non-pharmacological alternatives, such as Auricular Acupuncture.

Objective: Based on a review of randomised controlled trials, this study aims to provide an analysis of the effects and methodologies of auricular acupuncture for managing preoperative anxiety.

Results: The analysed studies suggest that auricular acupuncture has a therapeutic effect, leading to a significant decrease in anxiety levels. The intervention was found to be superior to sham or placebo interventions. It was also more effective at reducing intraoperative anaesthetic consumption compared to pharmacological treatments in one study. In a family-centred approach, the treatment was shown to reduce anxiety in children when administered to their parents. The most frequently used points were *Shenmen* and *Kidney*, suggesting this combination may be a particularly important therapeutic strategy. The therapy was consistently reported as safe with minimal adverse effects.

Conclusion: The available evidence supports the use of auricular acupuncture as a safe, effective, and well-tolerated method for reducing preoperative anxiety. Its ease of administration and proven clinical benefits make it a promising tool for patient care. Further research is warranted to address the limitations identified in the reviewed studies, paving the way for a more robust understanding of its clinical efficacy.

Keywords: Anxiety; Preoperative Anxiety; Auricular Acupuncture; Auriculoacupuncture; Ear Acupuncture; Complementary Therapies; Traditional Chinese Medicine.

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1. Introduction

Preoperative anxiety, a common and significant concern for patients undergoing surgical and medical procedures, is characterised by feelings of apprehension, tension, and worry related to the upcoming intervention ^{1,2}. This psychological state is a well-documented issue with potential negative effects on both patient experience and clinical outcomes ³. Preoperative anxiety can lead to increased stress, heightened pain perception, and a greater need for anaesthesia, which can contribute to higher rates of morbidity and mortality ^{4,5}.

Specifically, anxiety can manifest as increased heart rate, elevated blood pressure, and a heightened stress response, all of which can complicate the surgical process and recovery⁶. The impact extends beyond the patient, as parental anxiety is also a known contributor to a child's preoperative anxiety levels⁷, highlighting the need for a family-centred approach to care.

Historically, preoperative anxiety has been managed primarily through pharmacological interventions. While effective, these medications can be time-consuming to administer and may cause undesirable side effects^{5,8,9}. This has led to an increasing interest in exploring non-pharmacological alternatives, particularly for specific populations like pregnant women and pediatric patients¹⁰.

A study by Neves *et al.*¹¹, found that targeted stimulation of the central and peripheral regions of the auricular pavilion can induce a range of therapeutic effects. This includes behavioural inhibition, the mitigation of inflammatory responses, appetite suppression, and the enhancement of various physiological functions, such as cardiac performance. Furthermore, the research demonstrated positive outcomes in addressing conditions including depressive symptoms, epilepsy, and pain.

The auricle microsystem is usually associated with Auricular Acupuncture (or auriculoacupuncture and ear acupuncture), where diagnosis and treatment can be performed¹². Therefore, drawing upon evidence from randomised controlled trials, this study aims to analyse the effects and methodologies of auricular acupuncture in the context of preoperative anxiety.

2. Auricular Acupuncture for Preoperative Anxiety

2.1. Clinical Effects

Research has explored the use of auricular acupuncture to manage preoperative anxiety across various surgical and medical contexts. Clinical studies have reported its use for anxiety before cesarean section¹³ and cardiovascular interventions¹⁴, as well as procedures such as cholecystectomy¹⁵, totally extraperitoneal hernia repair¹⁵, and cancer surgery¹⁶. Furthermore, research has also assessed the use of parental auricular acupuncture to alleviate anxiety in children undergoing anaesthesia for a surgical procedure¹⁷.

Preoperative anxiety in patients undergoing cesarean section is a well-documented issue¹⁸, and non-pharmacological interventions are increasingly favoured in this population¹⁹⁻²¹. In a prospective, blind, and controlled trial, researchers investigated the anxiolytic effects of auricular acupuncture as a potential intervention¹³. Pregnant women scheduled for cesarean section under spinal anaesthesia were randomised into three groups: an auricular acupuncture group (receiving needles), a sham auricular acupuncture group (receiving an inert intervention without needles), and a usual care group (receiving no intervention).

The primary objective was to assess the change in anxiety levels, measured by a Visual Analogue Scale for Anxiety (VAS-A), between the pre-induction room (T0) and entering the operating room (T1). A key finding was the significant difference in anxiety variation between the auricular acupuncture and sham auricular acupuncture groups. While the auricular acupuncture group experienced a notable 19% decrease in anxiety, the sham group, in contrast, showed a 21% increase. This divergence highlights the specific therapeutic effect of the acupuncture intervention over a placebo. Furthermore, a clinically significant anxiety reduction (defined as a decrease of over 33%) was achieved by a proportion of patients in the auricular acupuncture group that was 2.5 times greater than that in the sham group, a statistically significant result ($p=0.02$).

Interestingly, the authors observed that the anxiolytic effect of auricular acupuncture was most pronounced in women who presented with a lower baseline level of anxiety. While the auricular acupuncture group demonstrated a trend toward improved anxiety levels compared to the usual care group, no statistically significant difference was found

in this comparison. Additionally, the study found no measurable effect of auricular acupuncture on parasympathetic tone, as assessed by heart rate variability, and no adverse effects were reported.

In a study addressing the need for effective non-pharmacological interventions to reduce preoperative anxiety in cardiovascular patients, researchers investigated the combined effect of auricular acupuncture and lavender oil aromatherapy¹⁴. The study, conducted as a randomised prospective trial, enrolled 80 patients undergoing various cardiovascular procedures, including coronary angiography, right heart catheterisation, and transcatheter valve replacements. These patients were divided into two groups: a verum group that received verum bilateral auricular acupuncture and lavender oil aromatherapy, and a "placebo" group that received a combination of sham acupuncture and a placebo oil.

The primary outcome was the change in state anxiety, measured using the Spielberger State Anxiety Inventory (STAI), from baseline to 30 minutes post-intervention. A key finding was the statistically significant reduction in anxiety in the verum group compared to the placebo group. The mean anxiety score in the verum group decreased by 4.18 points more than in the placebo group, with the difference reaching statistical significance ($p=0.047$). This result demonstrates the combined therapeutic effect of auricular acupuncture and lavender oil in reducing general state anxiety. Furthermore, a significantly higher proportion of patients in the verum group (87.2%) reported a perceived subjective treatment success compared to the placebo group (65.9%), reinforcing the clinical relevance of the intervention. While the combined treatment was effective in reducing general state anxiety, the study found no significant differences between the two groups in terms of procedure-specific anxiety or clinical blood pressure changes. No serious adverse events were reported, confirming the safety of the intervention.

Moreover, in a randomised, blinded, controlled trial, Wang *et al.*¹⁶ investigated the effectiveness of auricular acupuncture in reducing preoperative anxiety in adults undergoing elective ambulatory surgery. The study included 91 patients ranging in age from 19 to 66 who were scheduled for surgery for both benign and potentially malignant diseases.

Participants were randomised into three groups: a Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) auricular acupuncture group, an auricular acupuncture group, and a sham group. The TCM auricular acupuncture group received auricular acupuncture at points related to fear and anxiety. The auricular acupuncture group received acupuncture at points documented to produce relaxation, general sedation, and anxiety reduction. The sham group received needles at three points with no documented effect on anxiety. Each participant received the auricular acupuncture needles on the non-dominant side of their external ear for 30 minutes. Sedative premedication was not offered to any participants.

The primary outcome measure was a change in state anxiety, measured using the STAI. While the three groups had similar anxiety levels before the intervention, significant differences were found afterwards. Patients in the auricular acupuncture group showed significantly lower anxiety levels compared to the sham group ($P=0.01$). However, the anxiety levels of the TCM auricular acupuncture group did not differ significantly from either the sham group or the auricular acupuncture group. This may be attributed to the different theoretical framework of point selection, with the TCM group using points specifically related to fear, while the other group used points associated with general sedation and relaxation.

In a prospective study¹⁵, researchers sought to compare the effectiveness of acupuncture with pharmacological treatment in reducing preoperative anxiety in patients undergoing cholecystectomy or totally extraperitoneal hernia repair. The study enrolled 120 patients who were randomised into a pharmacological treatment group (receiving Midazolam), a somatic acupuncture group, and an auricular acupuncture group. A fourth group of 36 patients received no treatment. The primary endpoint was the level of intraoperative relaxation, which was indirectly measured by the consumption of Propofol and Fentanyl during anaesthesia. The secondary endpoint was the reduction of preoperative anxiety as measured by the Italian version of the STAI questionnaire.

The study found that patients in the somatic acupuncture and auricular acupuncture groups required significantly less Propofol compared to the pharmacological treatment group ($p=0.0019$ and $p=0.0016$, respectively). Additionally, somatic acupuncture patients used less Fentanyl than the pharmacological treatment group ($p=0.002$). No significant differences were observed in Propofol or Fentanyl consumption when comparing the somatic acupuncture and auricular acupuncture groups. Furthermore, no adverse events were reported for the acupuncture treatments, and the procedures were well tolerated.

Another study by Wang *et al.*¹⁷ investigated the effectiveness of parental auricular acupuncture as an adjunct for children's preoperative anxiety.

The study included 47 children scheduled for outpatient surgery, randomised into two groups. The intervention group's parents received auricular acupuncture, while the control group received sham acupuncture. The acupuncture needles were applied to the parents 30 minutes before their child's surgery. The primary outcome was a change in the children's anxiety levels, which were assessed using the modified Yale Preoperative Anxiety Scale (mYPAS) at three points: when the child first arrived, in the preoperative holding area, and upon entering the operating room. Secondary outcomes included the parents' anxiety levels, also measured using a VAS-A, and the amount of propofol required for the child's anaesthesia.

The results showed a significant decrease in anxiety in the children whose parents received auricular acupuncture, with the mYPAS scores in the intervention group dropping from 47.9 to 32.2. The control group, however, showed no significant change in their children's anxiety levels. This finding suggests that parental auricular acupuncture can be an effective way to indirectly reduce a child's preoperative anxiety. The study also found that the parents who received the acupuncture experienced a significant decrease in their own anxiety (from 51.5 to 30.7). No adverse events were reported in either group, confirming the safety of the intervention.

2.2. Clinical Methodologies

In this section, the clinical methodology regarding auricular acupuncture points is analysed (Table 1).

In this analysis, the study of Favre-Felix *et al.*¹³ was not considered, as the auricular acupuncture effects were not obviously superior to no treatment.

Table 1. Auricular acupuncture points used in each study.

Study	Auricular acupuncture points
Patsalis <i>et al.</i> ¹⁴	Bilateral Relaxation point
Zanella <i>et al.</i> ¹⁵	Triad Relax - <i>Shenmen</i> , Sensory Master, and Callous Body points.
Wang <i>et al.</i> ¹⁶	TCM auricular acupuncture group: Kidney, Heart, and <i>Shenmen</i> points. Auricular acupuncture group: Relaxation, Tranquilliser, and Master Cerebral points.
Wang <i>et al.</i> ¹⁷	Ipsilateral to the dominant hand <i>Shenmen</i> , Sympathetic, and Kidney points

According to the included studies, a total of 9 different points were used. Most studies employed a combination of points¹⁵⁻¹⁷, while only one used a single point¹⁴.

The most used point was *Shenmen*, used in three of the studies¹⁵⁻¹⁷. *Shenmen*, also known as the "Spirit Gate," is a point considered to tranquillise the mind^{22,23}.

Regarding heart rate variability, research has previously reported that this point is capable of keeping a low frequency/high frequency ratio at lower levels and high frequency at higher levels during the postoperative period in patients who had undergone hemicolectomy²⁴. Both indicators suggest a shift towards parasympathetic dominance, which is associated with a state of relaxation, calmness, and reduced stress^{25,26}.

Its location (Figure 1) is within the triangular fossa, which is the hollow, triangular-shaped depression in the upper part of the ear. It is generally described as being in the upper, inner portion of this fossa, just above where the antihelix ridge splits into two crus.

Figure 1. Ear *Shenmen* location.

However, two more points were commonly used twice in the included studies. Those were the Relaxation point^{14,16}, and the Kidney point^{16,17}.

The Relaxation point is located at the superior lateral wall of the triangular fossa (Figure 2), and its effects are usually associated with anxiety reduction and relaxation^{16,17}. The use of this point for anxiety has been relatively researched^{27,28}. For example, acupressure at this point has been shown to alleviate preoperative anxiety in patients undergoing gynaecological surgery²⁷. Another study showed that auricular acupressure at the relaxation point is effective for anxiety in the prehospital emergency setting²⁸.

Figure 2. Relaxation point location.

On the other hand, the Kidney point is a point used following the TCM theory. According to Rodrigues *et al.* ²⁹, anxiety is an intense apprehension, uncertainty and fear caused by anticipation, which, in TCM, the authors associate with the internal pathological agent 恐 (*kǒng*)/fear. Fear is associated with the Kidney in TCM ²⁹⁻³⁴.

The Kidney point is located in the centre of the ear, specifically in the cavum concha. Some sources describe its location more specifically as being below and slightly inward from the *Shenmen* point, tucked under the lower branch of the antihelix ridge (Figure 3). This point is commonly used in Auricular Acupuncture protocols for anxiety ³⁵⁻³⁷.

Figure 3. Kidney point location.

Despite the analysis focusing on the use of each point, the concurrent use is important to note (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Points used in association.

The predominant combination of auricular points was *Shenmen* and Kidney, suggesting that their combined effect may be a particularly important therapeutic strategy in the treatment of preoperative anxiety.

3. Final Remarks

Functional magnetic resonance imaging studies have been crucial for understanding the neurophysiological basis of auricular acupuncture¹².

In the study of Romoli *et al.*³⁸, the stimulation of the left Brain Stem auricular point resulted in activation of the pain matrix, with specific local differences in the left amygdala, anterior cingulate cortex, and cerebellum. These results align with the points' therapeutic uses for head pain, dizziness, and vertigo. These distinct activation patterns suggest point-specific effects¹².

Another example is the study of Alimi *et al.*³⁹, which observed that the stimulation of the hand auricular acupoint activated the somatosensory cortex for the hand. As well, the same authors found that stimulating the knee auricular point produced different brain activation patterns with potentially distinct neurophysiological and clinical effects.

In addition, Zhang *et al.*⁴⁰ observed that auricular acupuncture in stroke patients activated the primary motor cortex (M1), correlating with increased motor evoked potential amplitude and oxyhemoglobin levels.

The concept of the auricular reflex system being partly based on a connection to the vagus nerve dates back to Friedrich Arnold in 1832, who found that stimulating the external ear canal could induce a cough reflex similar to that of the vagal nerve. This suggests that the auricular branches of the vagus nerve may mediate some of the therapeutic effects of auriculotherapy^{41,42}.

In this study, the therapeutic efficacy and safety of auricular acupuncture for managing preoperative anxiety were examined across a range of surgical and medical contexts. The findings from multiple randomised controlled trials affirm that auricular acupuncture is a safe, well-tolerated, and effective anxiolytic intervention. In fact, the theory on the use of auricular points for anxiety has been increasingly studied, and benefits have been reported⁴³⁻⁴⁷.

In this review, the analysed studies suggest that Auricular Acupuncture possesses a clear therapeutic effect, with an observed decrease in anxiety levels in patients undergoing various surgeries. In several controlled trials, this effect was found to be superior to sham or placebo interventions.

As well, the research highlights auricular acupuncture as a valuable non-pharmacological alternative to traditional sedatives. Studies comparing it to pharmacological treatments found that both somatic and auricular acupuncture were more effective at reducing intraoperative anaesthetic consumption.

The intervention was also effective in a family-centred approach. Administering auricular acupuncture to parents was shown to significantly reduce the preoperative anxiety of their children, highlighting the broad potential of this method.

The used auricular points are varied; however, a finding from the clinical methodologies was the predominant use of a combination of the *Shenmen* and Kidney points, suggesting that their concurrent use may be particularly important.

Despite the promising results, the reviewed studies present several limitations that warrant consideration for future research. A common limitation was the small sample sizes, which limit the statistical power and the generalizability of the findings.

As well, the study by Zanella *et al.*¹⁵, for instance, was also limited by the use of different anesthesiologists, which could introduce variability in the administration of anaesthetic drugs and confound the results.

Furthermore, the use of combined therapies, as seen in the study by Patsalis *et al.*¹⁴, which combined acupuncture with aromatherapy, makes it difficult to isolate the specific contribution of auricular acupuncture alone. Future research should address these limita-

tions by employing larger, multicenter trials with rigorous blinding and standardised procedures to further validate the efficacy and mechanisms of auricular acupuncture for preoperative anxiety.

4. Conclusions

The available evidence from the reviewed trials provides support for the use of Auricular Acupuncture as a safe and effective method for reducing preoperative anxiety. Its ease of administration, minimal adverse effects, and proven clinical benefits make it a promising tool for improving patient care in the crucial moments before surgery. Future research is warranted to address the limitations identified in these studies, paving the way for a more robust understanding of auricular acupuncture's clinical efficacy.

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References

1. Sadock BJ, Sadock VA, Ruiz P. Comprehensive textbook of psychiatry: lippincott Williams & wilkins Philadelphia; 2000.
2. VandenBos GR. APA dictionary of psychology: American Psychological Association; 2007. 1591473802.
3. Nigussie S, Belachew T, Wolancho W. Predictors of preoperative anxiety among surgical patients in Jimma University Specialized Teaching Hospital, South Western Ethiopia. BMC Surg. 2014;14:67. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2482-14-67>
4. Maranets I, Kain ZN. Preoperative anxiety and intraoperative anesthetic requirements. Anesth Analg. 1999;89(6):1346-51. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1097/0000539-199912000-00003>
5. Baagil H, Baagil H, Gerbershagen MU. Preoperative Anxiety Impact on Anesthetic and Analgesic Use. Medicina [Internet]. 2023; 59(12). doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina59122069>
6. Britteon P, Cullum N, Sutton M. Association between psychological health and wound complications after surgery. Br J Surg. 2017;104(6):769-76. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/bjs.10474>
7. Kumari K, Nemani S, Rathod D, Sharma A, Bhatia PK, Goyal S. Prediction of correlation between preoperative parents' anxiety and their child's anxiety before elective surgery under anaesthesia: An observational study. Indian J Anaesth. 2024;68(9):809-14. doi: https://doi.org/10.4103/ija.ija_1269_23
8. Harris M, Chung F. Complications of general anesthesia. Clin Plast Surg. 2013;40(4):503-13. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cps.2013.07.001>

9. Brull R, McCartney CJ, Chan VW, El-Beheiry H. Neurological complications after regional anesthesia: contemporary estimates of risk. *Anesth Analg*. 2007;104(4):965-74. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1213/01.ane.0000258740.17193.ec>
10. Kisielewska W, Kosciolk M, Kowalczyk W, Mitura B, Mitura L, Rogula S, et al. Decreasing Preoperative Anxiety in Patients with Newly Available Multimodal Approaches-A Narrative Review. *J Clin Med*. 2025;14(9). doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm14092940>
11. Neves ML, Coutinho BD, da Silva EDC, Gentil LB, dos Santos ARS, da Silva MD. Ear acupuncture and neuromodulation: narrative review. *Longhua Chinese Medicine*. 2022;5.
12. Rodrigues JM, Simões K, Moreira O, Cruz G, Soares PB, Machado JP. Auricle reflex system: A practical approach to diagnosis and treatment. *Revista Internacional de Acupuntura*. 2024;18(1):100287. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acu.2024.100287>
13. Favre-Felix J, Laurent V, Branche P, Huissoud C, Raffin M, Pradat P, et al. Auricular Acupuncture for Preoperative Anxiety in Parturient Women with Scheduled Cesarean Section: A Randomized Placebo-Controlled Blind Study. *J Integr Complement Med*. 2022;28(7):569-78. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1089/jicm.2021.0346>
14. Patsalis PC, Malik-Patsalis AB, Rauscher HG, Schaefer C, Useini D, Strauch JT, et al. Efficacy of Auricular Acupuncture and Lavender Oil Aromatherapy in Reducing Preinterventional Anxiety in Cardiovascular Patients: A Randomized Single-Blind Placebo-Controlled Trial. *J Integr Complement Med*. 2022;28(1):45-50. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1089/jicm.2021.0171>
15. Zanella S, Buccelletti F, Vassiliadis A, De Bortoli R, Visentini S, Pedrotti G, et al. Preoperative anxiety management: acupuncture vs. pharmacological treatment - A prospective study. *Eur Rev Med Pharmacol Sci*. 2022;26(3):900-5. doi: https://doi.org/10.26355/eurrev_202202_27999
16. Wang SM, Peloquin C, Kain ZN. The use of auricular acupuncture to reduce preoperative anxiety. *Anesth Analg*. 2001;93(5):1178-80, table of contents. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1097/00000539-200111000-00024>
17. Wang SM, Maranets I, Weinberg ME, Caldwell-Andrews AA, Kain ZN. Parental auricular acupuncture as an adjunct for parental presence during induction of anesthesia. *Anesthesiology*. 2004;100(6):1399-404. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1097/00000542-200406000-00011>
18. Abd F. Preoperative Anxiety and Associated Factors Among Women Undergoing Cesarean Section: A Cross-Sectional Study. *International Journal of Body, Mind and Culture*. 2024;11(6):170-81. doi: <https://doi.org/10.61838/rmdn.ijbmc.11.6.20>
19. Walton GD, Ross LE, Stewart DE, Grigoriadis S, Dennis CL, Vigod S. Decisional conflict among women considering antidepressant medication use in pregnancy. *Arch Womens Ment Health*. 2014;17(6):493-501. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00737-014-0448-1>
20. Barker LC, Dennis CL, Hussain-Shamsy N, Stewart DE, Grigoriadis S, Metcalfe K, et al. Decision-making about antidepressant medication use in pregnancy: a comparison between women making the decision in the preconception period versus in pregnancy. *BMC Psychiatry*. 2020;20(1):54. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-020-2478-8>
21. Silverwood V, Bullock L, Jordan J, Turner K, Chew-Graham CA, Kingstone T, et al. Non-pharmacological interventions for the management of perinatal anxiety in primary care: a meta-review of systematic reviews. *BJGP Open*. 2023;7(3):BJGPO.2023.0022. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3399/BJGPO.2023.0022>
22. O'Connor J, Bensky D, yuan SZyx. *Acupuncture: A Comprehensive Text*: Eastland Press; 1981. 9780939616008.
23. Abbate S. *Chinese auricular acupuncture*: Taylor & Francis; 2015. 1040181732.
24. Arai YC, Sakakima Y, Kawanishi J, Nishihara M, Ito A, Tawada Y, et al. Auricular acupuncture at the "shenmen" and "point zero" points induced parasympathetic activation. *Evidence-based complementary and alternative medicine : eCAM*. 2013;2013(1):945063. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/945063>
25. Kiyono K, Hayano J, Watanabe E, Yamamoto Y. Heart Rate Variability (HRV) and Sympathetic Nerve Activity. In: Iwase S, Hayano J, Orimo S, editors. *Clinical Assessment of the Autonomic Nervous System*. Tokyo: Springer Japan; 2017. p. 147-61. 978-4-431-56010-4, 978-4-431-56012-8.

26. Ruediger H, Seibt R, Scheuch K, Krause M, Alam S. Sympathetic and parasympathetic activation in heart rate variability in male hypertensive patients under mental stress. *J Hum Hypertens*. 2004;18(5):307-15. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.jhh.1001671>
27. Luo L, Dai Q, Mo Y, Yan Y, Qian M, Zhuang X, et al. The effect of auricular acupressure on preoperative anxiety in patients undergoing gynecological surgery. *Int J Clin Exp Med*. 2016;9(2):4065-70.
28. Kober A, Scheck T, Schubert B, Strasser H, Gustorff B, Bertalanffy P, et al. Auricular acupressure as a treatment for anxiety in prehospital transport settings. *Anesthesiology*. 2003;98(6):1328-32. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1097/0000542-200306000-00005>
29. Rodrigues JM, Lopes L, Gonçalves M, Machado JP. Taijiquan and qigong as a mindfulness cognitive-behavioural based therapy on the treatment of cothymia in school-age children—A preliminary study. *Journal of bodywork and movement therapies*. 2021;26:329-38.
30. Lasca MM, Pereira AF, Rodrigues AP. Urinary Tract Infection and Mental Health – The Role of Dietotherapy and Traditional Chinese Medicine. *Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health*. 2024;2(2). doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13785988>
31. Lu Y, Lui C. *Concepts and Theories of Traditional Chinese Medicine*: Science Press; 1998. 9787030056733.
32. Windridge C, Xiaochun W. *The Fountain of Health: An A-Z of Traditional Chinese Medicine*: Mainstream Publishing; 1994. 9781851586356.
33. Stux G. *Background and Theory of Traditional Chinese Medicine*. In: Stux G, Pomeranz B, editors. *Basics of Acupuncture*. Heideberg, Germany: Springer; 1991. p. 56-66. 978-3-642-97280-5.
34. College JNM. *The dictionary of traditional Chinese medicine*. Shanghai Sci-Tech Press Shanghai; 1985.
35. Cunha J, Rodrigues VP, Frizzo HCF, Pires FK, Pereira AP, Aragao FBA, et al. The effect of auriculotherapy on individuals with anxiety in follow-up in Primary Health Care. *Rev Bras Enferm*. 2025;78(3):e20240186. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1590/0034-7167-2024-0186>
36. Lemos A, Lourenco BG, Chaves ECL, Toledo LV, Chianca TCM, Moura CC. Ear acupuncture with laser and needles in the treatment of anxiety in university students: a randomized clinical trial. *Revista da Escola de Enfermagem da U S P*. 2025;58:e20240239. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1980-220X-REEUSP-2024-0239en>
37. Araújo B, Moura C, Azevedo C, Mata L, Ruela L, Corrêa H. The effectiveness of ear acupuncture on quality of life and emotional disorders in nursing professionals during the covid-19 pandemic: a randomized clinical trial. *Curr Res Cmpl Alt Med*. 2023;7:213.
38. Romoli M, Allais G, Airola G, Benedetto C, Mana O, Giacobbe M, et al. Ear acupuncture and fMRI: a pilot study for assessing the specificity of auricular points. *Neurol Sci*. 2014;35 Suppl 1:189-93. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10072-014-1768-7>
39. Alimi D, Geissmann A, Gardeur D. Auricular acupuncture stimulation measured on functional magnetic resonance imaging. *Medical Acupuncture*. 2002;13(2):18-21.
40. Zhang J, Huang W, Chen Z, Jiang H, Su M, Wang C. Effect of auricular acupuncture on neuroplasticity of stroke patients with motor dysfunction: A fNIRS study. *Neurosci Lett*. 2023;812:137398. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neulet.2023.137398>
41. He W, Wang X, Shi H, Shang H, Li L, Jing X, et al. Auricular acupuncture and vagal regulation. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med*. 2012;2012.
42. Round R, Litscher G, Bahr F. Auricular acupuncture with laser. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med*. 2013;2013.
43. Gagliardi G, Meneghetti M, Ceccherelli F, Giommi A, Romoli M. Auricular Acupuncture for Anxiety in Health Care Volunteers: Randomized Crossover Study Comparing Real and Sham Needles. *Medical acupuncture*. 2014;26(3):161-6. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1089/acu.2014.1036>
44. Sisodia M, Kaur H, Garg N, Choudhary R, Yeluri R. The Effect of Three-point Acupressure Therapy on Anxiety Levels in Children Undergoing Dental Procedures. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent*. 2024;17(2):136-42. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5005/jp-journals-10005-2738>

45. Iunes DH, Chaves Ede C, Moura Cde C, Correa B, Carvalho LC, Silva AM, et al. Role of Auriculotherapy in the Treatment of Temporomandibular Disorders with Anxiety in University Students. Evidence-based complementary and alternative medicine: eCAM. 2015;2015:430143. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/430143>
46. Avisa P, Kamatham R, Vanjari K, Nuvvula S. Effectiveness of Acupressure on Dental Anxiety in Children. *Pediatr Dent*. 2018;40(3):177-83.
47. Agarwal A, Ranjan R, Dhiraaj S, Lakra A, Kumar M, Singh U. Acupressure for prevention of pre-operative anxiety: a prospective, randomised, placebo controlled study. *Anaesthesia*. 2005;60(10):978-81. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2044.2005.04332.x>